

Synthesis of 3-Hydroxy-2-(3'-pyridyl) Chromones and 2-(3'-pyridyl)-Chromones

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A few ethyl phenols and their corresponding 2'-hydroxy-acetophenones were synthesised from respective *o*-hydroxy-acetophenones and a few 3-hydroxy-2-(3'-pyridyl)chromones and 2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones were synthesised from *o*-hydroxy-acetophenones. The compounds were tested for their physiological activities.

ACRYLOPHENONES having a heterocyclic substituent at 3 positions are active against *M. tuberculosis* and *S. aureus*¹⁻⁹. 2-Phenyl and 2-methyl chromones are reported to possess pharmacological activity¹⁰⁻¹⁵. 6-Chloro-2-(2'-quinolyl) chromones are found to be active against sarcoma-180¹⁶. Taking into account these activities of acrylophenones and chromones having a heterocyclic substituent, a number of such compounds have been synthesised and results are reported in this paper.

Some new ethylphenols (I), used as starting materials, were prepared from substituted acetophenones by Clemmenson's reduction method. The various substituted acetophenones such as methyl-ethyl-halogeno-ethyl-2',4',5'-dichloro-, 2',4'-dibromo and -3', 4'-benzo-2'-hydroxy acetophenones (II) were prepared from the corresponding acetates by Fries reaction (Table 1). These acetophenones (II), on condensation with pyridine-3-aldehyde in basic medium yielded the corresponding 3-(3'-pyridyl)-acrylophenones (III). The acrylophenones (III) on treatment with alkaline hydrogen peroxide under Alger-Flynn-Oyamada reaction condition afforded the corresponding 3-hydroxy-2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones (IV). The acrylophenones (III) were subjected to oxidative ring closure by selenium dioxide to give the corresponding 2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones (V). The same 2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones (V) were also obtained by an alternative route. The acetophenones (II) were esterified by nicotiny chloride in dry pyridine. The resulting esters (VI) were converted into 1, 3-propanediones (VII) by Baker-Venkataraman transformation. 1, 3-Propanediones (VII) on cyclodehydration under acidic condition yielded the same 2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones (V) as were obtained by SeO₂ method. The identify was proved by mixed melting points which showed no depression.

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectra of a few compounds were scanned in nujol mull. (3'-Pyridyl)-2'-hydroxy-acrylophenones showed strong absorption bands in the region 1650-1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and 1610-1620 cm⁻¹ (C=C). The ir spectra of 2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones showed bands in the range

of 1630-1690 cm⁻¹ and 1560-1600 cm⁻¹, characteristic of chromone carbonyl and ethylinic double bond respectively.

Physiological activity : Some ethyl phenols (I) methyl substituted 2'-hydroxy acrylophenones (II), 3-hydroxy-2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones (IV) and 2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones (V) have been tested for their physiological activity. 2-Ethyl-5-chlorophenol was found to be toxic. Some acrylophenones (III) have been tested for anti-trichnella spiralis, antiviral, antithrilis, gastric secretion, pylorus ligation etc., but none of them was found to be active. 3-Hydroxy-2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones (IV) and 2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones (V) have been tested for gastric secretion, pylorus ligation and anthalmentic activities. Only 2-(3'-pyridyl)-6-8-dichloro chromones have shown anthelmentic activity.

Experimental

(1) *Ethyl substituted phenols (I)* : A mixture of amalgamated zinc (80 g), hydrochloric acid (2 : 3 v/v ; 300 ml) and alcoholic solution of 2'-hydroxy acetophenone (20 g), was refluxed for 54 hr. Concentrated hydrochloric acid was added in small

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TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF ETHYL PHENOLS (I), CORRESPONDING PHENYL ACETATES AND 2'-HYDROXY-ACETOPHENONES (II), ACRYLOPHENONES (III), 3-HYDROXY-2-(3'-PYRIDYL) CHROMONES (IV); 2-(3'-PYRIDYL) CHROMONES (V); 2-(3'-PYRIDILOXY) ACETOPHENONES (VI) AND 1 : 2 PROPANE DIONES (VII)

Phenols Used	m.p.(b p.) °C	Yield %	Corresponding Compounds			
			Phenyl Acetate		2'-Hydroxy-acetophenone (II)	
			b.p. °C	Yield %	m.p.(b.p.) °C	Yield %
6-ethyl-3-methyl	(218)	40	228	40	(270)	30
6-ethyl-4-methyl	(210)	50	232	60	(260)	40
3-chloro-6-ethyl	49	30	244	50	(258)	40
4-chloro-6-ethyl	(241)	50	227	70	(265)	50
4-bromo-6-ethyl	(163/10 mm.)	50	248	60	42	40

2'-Hydroxy-acetophenones Used	Corresponding Compounds									
	Compound III		Compound IV		Compound V		Compound VI		Compound VII	
	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %
3',5'-dibromo	210 ^g	90	238 ^e	40	230 ^L	40	151 ^e	50	158 ^d	60
3',5'-dichloro	185 ^f	80	262 ^e	50	223 ^L	50	112 ^f	40	98 ^e	40
3',6'-dichloro	174 ^g	60	115 ^e	40	191 ^L	30	125 ^d	50	136 ^d	30
3',4'-benzo	108 ^j	80	267 ^d	50	218 ^L	60	74 ^g	60	160 ^d	20
3'-ethyl-5'-chloro	160 ^k	80	39 ^e	80	172 ^L	30	82 ^h	70	168 ^e	50
3'-ethyl-6'-chloro	125 ^f	50	58 ^d	60	47 ^L	20	41 ^c	20	126 ^b	30
3'-ethyl-5'-bromo	94 ^h	50	43 ^e	25	68 ^L	40	32 ^e	20	138 ^b	50
3'-ethyl-5'-methyl	38 ⁱ	40	85 ^d	20	102 ^L	30	35 ^a	40	167 ^e	35
3'-ethyl-6'-methyl	41 ^h	50	67 ^c	30	123 ^L	20	38 ^b	30	140 ^d	20

a=20% acetic acid
 b=25% acetic acid
 c=30% acetic acid
 d=40% acetic acid
 e=50% acetic acid
 f=60% acetic acid
 g=70% acetic acid
 h=50% ethyl alcohol
 i=70% ethyl alcohol
 j=80% ethyl alcohol
 k=90% ethyl alcohol
 L=dioxane

The elemental analysis of above compounds for C and H gave satisfactory results.

quantities (20 ml) at intervals. The thick oily layer was worked up as usual and purified by distillation.

(2) *Substituted-2'-hydroxy acetophenones (II)*: A mixture of phenol (10 g), acetic anhydride (36 ml) and fused sodium acetate (8 g) was refluxed for 2 hr. The cold reaction mixture was poured on ice-water and phenyl acetate was isolated as usual. The phenyl acetate (10 g) so obtained was treated with powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride and was heated on an oil bath for 2 hr. 2-Hydroxy acetophenones formed were isolated by steam distillation.

(3) *3-(3'-Pyridyl) acrylophenones (III)*: A 50% solution of potassium hydroxide (5 ml) was added dropwise to a cold solution of pyridine-3-aldehyde (0.3 mole) and 2'-hydroxy acetophenone (0.2 mole) in ethanol (30 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 hr and poured over crushed ice containing enough acetic acid. The resulting solid was filtered,

washed with water, 5% NaHCO₃ solution and again with water. These compounds were crystallised from proper solvents.

(4) *3-Hydroxy-2-(3'-pyridyl) chromone (IV)*: To a cold solution of acrylophenones (0.0014 mole) in methanol (15 ml) was added a 16% solution of sodium hydroxide (2 ml) followed by dropwise addition of H₂O₂ (15% ; 2 ml). The reaction mixture was kept in an ice-chest overnight and the alkaline filtrate was acidified with acetic acid. The precipitated solid was then filtered, washed with water and crystallised from a proper solvent.

(5) *2-(3'-Pyridyl) chromones (V)*: A mixture of acrylophenone (0.003 mole), selenium dioxide (1 g) and amyl alcohol (15 ml) was refluxed for 10 hr. The hot solution was filtered and amyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation. The solids, 2-(3'-pyridyl) chromones, were crystallised from proper solvents.

(6) *1,3-Propanediones (VII)* : To an ice-cold solution of 2'-hydroxy acetophenones (II) (0.035 mole) in dry pyridine (10 ml), nicotiny chloride (0.04 mole) was added dropwise with stirring. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 7 hr at room temperature and then poured over crushed ice containing acetic acid. The resulting esters (VI), were crystallised from proper solvents. A cold mixture of the above ester (VI) (0.45 mole), dry pyridine (15 ml), powdered potassium hydroxide (2 g) was stirred for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice containing acetic acid. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from a proper solvent.

(7) *2-(3'-Pyridyl) chromones (V) from 1,3-propanediones (VII)* : A mixture of conc. sulphuric acid (10 ml), 1,3-propanedione (0.04 mole) and chloroform (40 ml) was stirred for 20 min. The reaction mixture was poured over ice-water and then made alkaline by cold sodium hydroxide solution. The chloroform layer was evaporated and the resulting solid was crystallised from a proper solvent.

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